

Analyzing Crime Statistics in the Municipality of San Jose and Goa Camarines Sur, Philippines AY 2019-2021

Ariel B. Barreda

University of the Cordilleras, Baguio City, Philippines
Graduate School, College of Criminal Justice Education

Abstract:- A crime is any action that is considered to be a public infraction. In states where the criminal common law is still in effect, the common law may also be used to provide the elements of a crime in addition to those found in statutes. The primary objective of this essay is to analyze, compare the crime statistics and explain the nature of crime in the Philippines AY 2019-2021. The data sources from San Jose and Goa Municipal Police Station. According to data, five hundred forty-four (544), out of seven hundred thirty-eight (738) were reported in Goa Municipal Police Station, while one hundred ninety-four (194) was reported in San Jose Municipal Police Station. Traffic Incidents, however, accounted for the greatest number of cases reported in Goa (212), while Special Law Violations accounted for the greatest number of cases reported in San Jose Police Station. The results show that there was a significant difference in the quantity of traffic accidents that occurred in San Jose and Goa, Camarines Sur, between 2019 and 2021. In contrast to San Jose, which had 36 reported incidents, Goa, Camarines Sur, had 212. In 2019 or during the pre-pandemic level in both the relevant municipality, more cases were documented, particularly those involving bodily injuries and property damage during the pandemic level. The findings imply that the geographical location and population density influence the number of cases reported to the relevant municipality. As a result, the municipal police offices in San Jose and Goa, Camarines Sur are adjacent municipalities, and the number of cases reported in the respected police offices is similar.

Keywords:- Analyzing, Crime Statistics, in the Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

A criminal act is one that is forbidden by the law. It entails doing someone else harm or causing damage to their property, especially public assets. Threats and harassment, domestic abuse, thievery, unlawful possession of weapons or drugs, cybercrime, and violent crimes like sexual assault, homicide, or human trafficking are only a few examples of crime actions. In 2021 About 375.73 thousand criminal incidents were reported in the Philippines. This represents a decrease from the overall number of roughly 395 thousand in the prior year. In terms of crime, violence, and terrorism, the Philippines has a mediocly high rate. The nation was ranked

fifth in the entire region in 2021 according to the order and security index.

Greater concentrations of people and places with higher unemployment rates were associated with higher crime rates in disadvantaged communities. (Statistista Research Department, November 23, 2022)

Violence makes it difficult for people to live in safety and security and can perpetuate poverty traps in many areas, according to Rachael Diprose (2007). The dearth of trustworthy and comparable statistics on the prevalence and type of violence is a major obstacle for academics, policymakers, and practitioners working across programs aiming at poverty reduction, including violence prevention. Even though they are forbidden by law, some crimes are regarded as mala prohibita (bad because they are forbidden), even though they are not necessarily terrible. Other crimes are viewed as mala in se, or "bad in themselves"; by conventional standards, these are seen as innately evil. Initially, common law offenses were justified under the concept of mala in se. Mala in se, however, includes a wide range of offenses that are now illegal according to the law. Criminal justice agencies use hot spots policing, which focuses on localized areas where crime is concentrated and where police can concentrate their efforts and use conventional law enforcement techniques to disrupt the crime event. These techniques are used to increase the effectiveness of crime detection (Braga, 2005; Sherman, 1995) According to Chalfin, A., & McCrary (2013), there is a direct correlation between police presence and rates of homicide, rape, robbery, assault, break-in, larceny, and theft of motor vehicles. According to their research, the elasticity for violent and property crimes is, respectively, -0.34 and -0.17. These trends inspire the researcher to analyze and compare the crime rates in the municipalities of San Jose and Goa, Camarines Sur. The primary goal of this study is to analyze and contrast the crime rates in the municipalities of San Jose and Goa, Camarines Sur, as well as to ascertain the types of crimes that are most frequently reported to the local police stations in each location, namely crimes against persons, crimes against property, non-index crimes, traffic incidents, and special laws. Identify potential areas for further investigation as well.

➤ *Purpose of this Study*

The main goal of this study is to analyze and compare the crime rates in the municipalities of San Jose and Goa, Camarines Sur, as well as to identify the types of crimes that are most frequently reported to the local police departments, namely crimes against persons, crimes against property, non-index crimes, traffic incidents, and special laws and specify the potential direction of future research.

II. METHODOLOGY

➤ *Study Sites*

This research was carried out in the Philippine cities of San Jose and Goa in the Camarines Sur province. The analysis of crime data statistics for the AYs 2019 and 2021 is the primary goal of this study. The province of Camarines Sur contains the seaside municipality of San Jose.48.04 square

kilometers (18.55 square miles) or 0.87% of Camarines Sur's total area make up the municipality's land area. The 2020 Census found that it had a population of 43,973. This amounted to 2.13% of Camarines Sur province's entire population or 0.72% of the entire Bicol Region's population. Based on these data, the population density is estimated to be 915 people per square kilometer, or 2,371 people per square mile. While Goa is a municipality in the Camarines Sur coast province. 206.18 square kilometers, or 79.61 square miles, or 3.74% of Camarines Sur's total area, are covered by the municipality's land area. According to the 2020 Census, 71,368 people called it home. This amounted to 1.17% of the population of the Bicol Region or 3.45% of the entire Camarines Sur province's population. A population density of 346 people per square kilometer, or 896 people per square mile, is calculated using these data.

Fig 1: Map of San Jose and Goa, Camarines Sur

➤ *Data Gathering Tools*

In order to collect their primary data, the researchers wrote a letter asking the San Jose Municipal Police Station and the Goa Police Station for the crime statistics records from 2019 to 2021. The researchers used the provided record to gather data, which they then examined, totaled, and tabulated to reach their goals, which were to examine and contrast the recognized Municipality's crime statistics.

➤ *Methods and Procedures*

Before data was collected, permission to perform the study was requested from the relevant authorities, such as the chief of police of the Goa Police Station and the San Jose Municipal Police Station. Data were presented in table format and analyzed using descriptive statistical techniques in order to preserve the privacy of the information. This research used documentary analysis to explore and assess the crime statistics in the Municipalities of San Jose and Goa,

Camarines Sur, as part of a comparative study of crime data in two municipalities.

➤ *Ethical Considerations*

The researcher will be writing the required letters of request or communication to the relevant office. If approved, a request for the study's conduct will be addressed to the relevant office. After that, verbal coordination with the police chiefs of the Municipal Police Station and Goa Police Station

will be made, and the responders will be given the assurance that their information would stay private. Finally, all of the data that had been collected for the quantitative analysis had been prepared and safeguarded.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Crimes Against Persons

Table1: Comparative Data Statistics on Crimes Against Person in Municipality of San Jose and Goa, Camarines Sur AY 2019-2021

Nature of Crime	San Jose Municipal Police Station,				Goa, Municipal Police Station				Total	Ranking
	2019	2020	2021	Total	2019	2020	2021	Total		
Crime Against Person										
Rape	15	7	10	32	14	11	12	37	69	1
Physical Injury	4	2	0	6	13	4	0	17	23	2
Murder	1	1	1	3	2	3	2	7	10	3
Homicide	0	1	1	2	0	1	0	1	3	4
Parricide	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	5.5
Rape W/Homicide	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	5.5
Infanticide	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.5
Kidnapping W/Homicide	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.5
Kidnapping W/Rape	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.5
Total	20	11	12	43	30	19	15	64	107	

Source: *San Jose Municipal Police Station, Province of Camarines Sur*

Crimes Against Persons refers to criminal offenses that typically involve bodily harm, the threat of bodily harm, or other actions committed against an individual's will. Rape, physical injury, murder, homicide, parricide, rape w/ homicide, infanticide, kidnapping w/ homicide, kidnapping w/ rape were all involved. This table1 compares the crime statistics for the Municipalities of San Jose and Goa in the Camarines Sur AY 2019–2021. Out of (107) crimes against person, rape (69), physical injury (23), murder (10), homicide (3), parricide (1), and rape with homicide (1) (64) were registered in the Goa Municipal Police Station, according to the results. In the San Jose Police Station, (43) was noted. However, out of the 107 crimes against person reported, rape accounted for the highest number with 69 (out of 107); see Table 1. (Rank 1). Compared to homicide (1) and rape with homicide (1), (Rank 4). The following crimes, such as infanticide, kidnapping with homicide, and kidnapping with rape, were oddly not reported.

In the Municipality of San Jose, Camarines Sur, from 2019 (20) to 2021(12), rape with homicide decreased, whereas in the Municipality of Goa, Camarines Sur, based on the statistics shown in table 1, the number of serious crimes against people decreased from 2019(30) to 2021. Serious crimes against people include murder, homicide, bodily injuries, parricide, and rape with homicide (15). However, rape was the most common crime against a person reported in this table 1 out of a total of 107 (69). (Rank 1). While

parricide (1) was committed, rape with homicide (1) was committed (rank 4). Surprisingly, there were no reported cases of infanticide, kidnapping with homicide, or kidnapping with rape. The findings suggested that population density and geographic location have an impact on the volume of cases reported to the respected municipality. As a result, there is little variation in the number of cases submitted to the respected police office between the municipal police offices in San Jose and Goa, Camarines Sur, which is the next municipality. Chalfin, A., & McCrary (2013) discovered a significant inverse relationship between the quantity of police and rates of homicide, rape, robbery, assault, break-in, larceny, and theft of motor vehicles. The elasticity in their study is -0.34 for violent crimes and -0.17 for property crimes, respectively. In addition, various demographic factors, including population density, the proportion of young men, education, marriage, and immigration, were discovered to be related to both crime rates. Vio Jianu Mojica, Adelbert Choi, Robert Neil Leong, and Frumencio Co (2019). It is advised that these findings be included in crime monitoring systems in order to help with resource allocation and program planning for better crime prevention and security management. These findings could be effective indicators of crime incidence. R. Broadhurst (2002) The prevalence of murder-robberies, mayhem, political violence, and banditry pose a serious threat to social and economic growth. The report also describes the nature of violence and crime.

B. Crimes Against Properties

Table 2: Comparative Data Statistics on Crimes Against Property in San Jose and Goa, Municipal Police Station AY 2019-2021

Nature of Crime	San Jose Municipal Police Station,				Goa, Municipal Police Station				Total	Ranking
	2019	2020	2021	Total	2019	2020	2021	Total		
Crime Against Property										
Theft	1	0	4	5	19	2	12	33	38	1
Robbery	3	1	1	5	15	3	8	26	31	2
Carnapping Motor Cycle	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	3
Robbery W/Homicide	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.5
Robbery W/Rape	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.5
Robbery W/Serious Physical Injuries	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.5
Robbery W/Arson	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.5
Robbery in Band	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.5
Carnapping Motor Vehicle	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.5
Arson W/Homicide	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.5
Cattle Rustling	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.5
Total	4	1	5	10	34	5	21	60	70	

Source: San Jose Municipal Police Station, Province of Camarines Sur

Statistics on property crimes in the Philippines from 2019 to 2021, broken down by kind, published on November 15, 2022 by Statista. The most instances of property crimes in the Philippines were committed by stealing in 2021. There were approximately 11.5 thousand theft instances in this year. Overall, compared to the prior year, a considerable decrease was seen in the number of crimes against property across the nation. In this paper, crime against property refers to any criminal act that typically involves property crimes or deprivation of property against the owner's will. Theft, robbery, carnapping motor cycle and motor vehicle, robbery with homicide, robbery with rape, robbery with serious physical injuries, robbery with arson, robbery in band, arson with homicide, and cattle rustling were all common charges.

Table 2 compares data statistics on property crimes in San Jose and Goa, Municipal Police Station AY 2019-2021. Data showed that (60) of the (70) property crimes were reported to the Goa Municipal Police Station. While (10) were reported to the San Jose Municipal Police Station. It's worth noting that none of the following incidents were recorded during the study period: robbery with homicide, robbery with rape, robbery with serious physical injuries, robbery with arson, robbery in band, carnapping with a motor vehicle, arson with homicide, and cattle rustling.

According to table 2's data for the AY 2019 to 2021, there was a significant difference between the municipalities of San Jose and Goa, Camarines Sur in terms of reported crimes against persons: in San Jose, Camarines Sur, there were only 10 reported crimes against persons, whereas in Goa, Camarines Sur, there were 60 reported crimes against persons. These crimes include theft, robbery, theft, carnapping, and motorcycle theft. This result suggested that the PNP Thrust and Program of 2022, which sustains aggressive police operation to improve public order and safety in our community and also sustains partnerships with local and institutional stakeholders in the campaign against criminality, terrorism, and illegal drugs, among other things, are the program projects and activities of the Philippine National Police in the respective municipal police office. R. Diprose (2007) to supplement the information already available on the frequency of violence against people and property as well as people's feelings of safety and security. Even though the causation chain's direction is debatable, if not circular, violence and poverty are inexorably intertwined.

C. Non- Index Crime

Table 3: Comparative Data Statistics on Non- Index Crime in San Jose and Goa, Municipal Police Station Province of Camarines Sur AY 2019-2021

Nature of Crime	San Jose Municipal Police Station,				Goa, Municipal Police Station				Total	Ranking
	2019	2020	2021	Total	2019	2020	2021	Total		
Non- Index Crime										
Acts of Lasciviousness	4	31	2	36	1	1	3	5	41	1
Frustrated/Attempted Homicide	1	4	4	9	4	2	0	6	15	2
Resisting Authorities	0	11	0	11	0	0	0	0	11	3
Other forms of Swindling	0	0	0	0	6	4	0	10	10	4
Alarms &Scandals	1	0	1	2	2	4	1	7	9	5
Direct Assaults	2	3	0	5	1	0	1	2	7	6.5

Grave Threats	2	3	0	5	0	2	0	2	7	6.5
Swindling (Estafa)	1	0	0	1	3	1	1	5	6	8
Frustrated/Attempted Murder	1	0	0	1	2	1	0	3	4	9.5
Qualified Trespass	0	0	0	0	3	1	0	4	4	9.5
Adultery	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	3	3	11.5
Malicious Mischief	1	0	0	1	0	0	2	2	3	11.5
Slander (Oral Defamation)	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	3	3	11.5
Consented Abduction	0	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	2	13.5
Frustrated/Attempted Rape /Anti Rape Law of 1997	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	2	2	13.5
Other Light Threats	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	2	13.5
Unjust Vexations	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	15.5
Concubinage	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	15.5
Frustrated/Attempted Parricide	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	15.5
Intriguing Against Honor	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	15.5
Sexual Assault	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	15.5
Other forms of Trespass	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	15.5
Altering Boundaries /Landmark	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	15.5
Disloyalty of Pub. Officers	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5
False Testimony Other Cases	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5
Violation Domicile	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5
Discharge of Firearms	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5
Simple Imprudence	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5
Illegal Cockfighting	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5
Frustrated Robbery	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5
Total	14	53	11	78	27	20	10	57	135	

Source: San Jose and Goa Municipal Police Station, Province of Camarines Sur

Infractions of Special Laws and the Revised Penal Code (Republic Act No. 3815) are classified as Non-Index Crimes since they are not regarded as index crimes. Non-index crimes are those that violate specific laws, such as those relating to illegal drugs, violence against women and children, child abuse, the traffic code, the use of firearms, illegal gambling, illegal logging, juvenile activities, and illegal fishing, and are included in this study. Additionally, this covers additional non-index offenses like threats, scandal, alarm, malicious mischief, estafa, acts of lewdness, unjust vexation, direct assault, adultery, abortion, and arson.

In the Camarines Sur province, the municipal police stations of San Jose and Goa have non-index crime statistics for the years 2019 to 2021 as presented in table 3. Data revealed that out of the one hundred thirty-five (135) cases, 78 (of them) were reported to the San Jose Municipal Police

Station and 57 (of them) to the Goa Municipal Police Station. As an illustration, consider the following: Acts of lasciviousness (36)(5), Frustrated/Attempted Homicide (9)(5), Resisting to Authorities (11)(0), Other Forms of Swindling (0)(10), Alarms & Scandals (2)(7), Direct Assaults (5)(2), Grave Threats (5)(2), Swindling (Estafa) (1)(5), Frustrated/Attempted Murder (1)(3), Qualified Trespass (0)(1).Unexpectedly, there are no cases of the following offences, namely Disloyalty of Public Officers, False Testimony Other Cases, and Violation, in the records. Acts of lasciviousness were, nevertheless, the most frequently reported non-Index offences in the San Jose Camarines Sur municipality. Other types of swindling, on the other hand, are frequently performed non-Index crimes in Goa Camarines Sur.

D. Traffic Incidents

Table 4: Comparative Data on Traffic Incidents in San Jose and Goa Municipal Police Station AY 2019-2021

Nature of Crime	San Jose Municipal Police Station,				Goa, Municipal Police Station				Total	Ranking
	2019	2020	2021	Total	2019	2020	2021	Total		
Traffic Incidents										
RIR Physical Injury	13	5	6	25	82	27	10	119	144	1
RIR Damage to Property	3	0	3	6	52	29	8	89	95	2
RIR Homicide	2	1	2	5	4	0	0	4	9	3
Total	18	6	11	36	138	56	18	212	248	

Source: San Jose Municipal Police Station, Province of Camarines Sur

Traffic incidents are unanticipated events that happen along the road that might interrupt or block normal traffic flow. The safety of incident responders and the general traveling public are both put at risk by traffic accidents, which increase the likelihood of additional collisions. The effectiveness of the transportation system and the dependability of travel are both impacted by incidents. One of the main responsibilities of transportation and public safety organizations is the safe and fast disposal of traffic incidents.

In this table 4, for the years 2019 to 2021, comparative data statistics on traffic incidents at San Jose and Goa Municipal Police Station in the province of Camarines Sur are presented. Results indicate that out of 248 reported traffic incidents, 212 were recorded at the Goa Police Station and 36 at the San Jose Police Station. As indicated in table 4, the findings demonstrate that there was a substantial variation in the number of traffic events that happened between 2019 and 2021 in San Jose and Goa, Camarines Sur. There were 36 reported incidents in San Jose, compared to 212 in Goa, Camarines Sur. However, the number of cases recorded in 2019 or at the pre-pandemic level in each municipality is higher in 2020 and 2021; in particular, there are more cases of physical injuries (13)(82) and property damage (3)(52) during the pandemic level.

Due to the community's continued daily operations, it was inferred by these statistics that there were more traffic incidents prior to the pandemic (2019). The results are shown in table 4, which shows that there was a discernible difference

in the quantity of traffic accidents that occurred between 2019 and 2021 in San Jose and Goa, Camarines Sur. In Goa, Camarines Sur, 212 reported incidents were reported as opposed to 36 in San Jose. In 2019 or at the pre-pandemic level, the number of cases reported in each municipality was higher, particularly those involving bodily injuries (13)(82) and property damage (35)(52) during the pandemic level. Because the community's regular activities are still ongoing, it was inferred by these results that there were more traffic incidents prior to the pandemic (2019). The results are shown in table 4, which shows that there was a significant difference in the quantity of traffic accidents that occurred in San Jose and Goa, Camarines Sur, between 2019 and 2021. In contrast to San Jose, which had 36 reported incidents, Goa, Camarines Sur, had 212. In 2019 or during the pre-pandemic level in both the relevant municipality, more cases were documented, particularly those involving bodily injuries (13)(82) and property damage (35)(52) during the pandemic level.

The regular flow of traffic may be interrupted or obstructed by the unforeseen occurrences that occur along the route. Traffic crashes increase the likelihood of additional collisions and put the safety of emergency responders as well as the general traveling public at risk. The reliability of travel and the effectiveness of the transportation system are both impacted by incidents. One of the main responsibilities of organizations involved in transportation and public safety is the safe and fast clearance of traffic incidents.

E. Special Laws

Table 5: Comparative Data Statistics on Special Laws in San Jose and Goa, Municipal Police Station AY 2019-2021

Nature of Crime	San Jose Municipal Police Station,					Goa, Municipal Police Station				Total	Ranking
	2019	2020	2021	2022	Total	2019	2020	2021	Total		
Special Laws											
Anti-VAWC Act 2004	14	7	4	1	26	34	12	4	50	76	1
Anti – Gambling Law	1	8	7	4	20	3	10	6	19	39	2
Comprehensive Dangerous Drug Act 2002	4	0	0	1	5	10	10	7	27	32	3
Anti-Child Abuse Law	4	4	3	0	11	10	4	3	17	28	4
Comprehensive Law on Firearms and Ammunition (RA105910)	1	0	0	0	1	5	0	7	12	13	5
Law on Reporting Communicable Diseases RA 11332	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	3	12	12	6
Comp. Dang. Drugs 2002 Sale/Trade/Admin	0	3	2	0	5	0	0	0	0	5	7
Coconut Preservation Act 1995	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	4	4	8.5
Illegal Logging	0	1	0	0	1	0	3	0	3	4	8.5
Bouncing Check Law	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	2	10.5
Cybercrime	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	2	10.5
Revised Forestry Code of the Phils.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	2	10.5
Illegal Numbers Game	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	12.5
Animal Welfare Act of 1998	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	12.5
Anti- Fencing Law of 1979	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.5

Anti – Trafficking in Person Act 2003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.5
Anti-Photo & Video Voyeurism Act 2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.5
Bayanihan Heal as On Act RA 11469	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.5
Chain Saw Act 2002	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.5
Cockfighting Law of 1974	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.5
Food/Drug Admin. Act 2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.5
Illegal Fishing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.5
Illegal Position of weapon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.5
Obstruction of Prosecution. of Criminals	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.5
Anti – Hazing Law	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.5
Anti – Terrorism Act of 2020 RA 11479	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.5
Omnibus Election Code of the Phil.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.5
Total	21	23	17	6	67	63	50	38	149	216	

Source: San Jose and Goa Municipal Police Station, Province of Camarines Sur

Special Law is also known as local law, special legislation, and it is a law that only applies to a specific location or specifically to a specific member or members of a class of people or things in the same situation but not to the entire class. It is also unconstitutional if the classification made is arbitrary or lacks a reasonable or legitimate justification or basis. Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). A law that has no time limits, is applicable throughout the entire country, is controlled by the legislature that passed it, and is applicable to all members of the same class also known as a general statute or act. Merriam-Webster. (n.d.).

The Municipal Police Station, AY 2019–2021, has provided comparative data statistics on Special Laws in San

Jose and Goa in Table 5. Data showed that out of two hundred and sixty-six (266), one hundred forty-nine (149) were reported in the Goa Municipal Police Station, while sixty-seven were recorded in the San Jose Municipal Police Station. However, the Anti-Violence Against Women Act of 2004 (76), Anti-Gambling Law (36), and Comprehensive Dangerous Drug Act of 2002 (32) in each municipality saw the most instances of special law violations. A breach of the Anti-Fencing Law of 1979, the Anti-Trafficking in Persons Act of 2003, the Anti-Terrorism Act of 2020 (RA 11479), the Omnibus Election Code of the Philippines, illegal fishing, etc., is not recorded as having occurred within that time.

Table 6: Summary of Comparative Data in San Jose and Goa, Municipal Police Station AY 2019- 2021

Nature of Crime	San Jose Municipal Police Station,				Goa, Municipal Police Station				Total	Ranking
	2019	2020	2021	Total	2019	2020	2021	Total		
Traffic Incidents	18	6	11	35	138	56	18	212	247	1
Special Laws	24	23	17	64	63	50	38	151	215	2
Crime Against Person	20	11	12	43	29	19	16	64	107	3
Non-Index Crime	16	15	11	42	27	20	10	57	99	4
Crime Against Property	4	1	5	10	34	5	21	60	70	5
Total	82	56	56	194	291	150	103	544	738	

Source: San Jose and Goa Municipal Police Station, Province of Camarines Sur

In this table, you will find a summary of comparative data in San Jose and Goa, Municipal Police Station AY 2019-2021. According to data, five hundred forty-four (544), out of seven hundred thirty-eight (738) were reported in Goa Municipal Police Station, while one hundred ninety-four (194) was reported in San Jose Municipal Police Station. Traffic Incidents, however, accounted for the greatest number of cases reported in Goa (212), while Special Law Violations accounted for the greatest number of cases reported in San Jose Police Station. Considering that the 2020 Census found

71,368 individuals residing in Goa. This was equal to either 1.17% of the entire Bicol Region's population or 3.45% of the entire province of Camarines Sur. According to the 2020 Census, San Jose Camarines Sur has a population of 43,973. This was the same as 2.13% of Camarines Sur's total population or 0.72% of the population of the entire Bicol Region. R. Soares (2004) Crime is unaffected by development once the existence of the reporting inaccuracy is taken into account. Lower crime rates are related to decreased inequality, higher growth, and improved education.

However, traffic incidents made up the majority of the cases reported in Goa (212), while violations of special laws made up the majority of the cases reported at San Jose Police Station. Since the 2020 Census found that 71,368 people called Goa home. This amounted to 1.17 percent of the Bicol region's total population or 3.45 percent of Camarines Sur province's total population. While the 2020 Census indicates that San Jose Camarines Sur has a population of 43,973. This amounted to 0.72% of the population of the Bicol Region or 2.13% of the overall population of Camarines Sur. Traffic incidents rank #1 overall among reported incidents, while property crimes come in at number five. According to the findings, San Jose and Goa Camarines Sur had the highest numbers of cases in 2019, indicating that they were at a pre-pandemic threshold. These findings suggested that the number of reported cases and those at the local police station are influenced by population density. The municipality's geographic location will also have an impact. Last but not least, the municipality's local police force must operate strictly. Similar findings to Dio, R. V. ., Apostol, S. M. G., & Madrazo, A. L. (2019) The number of crimes committed in the province decreased noticeably once Project Double Barrel was put into place. However, the crime solution efficiency (CSE) is not significantly different from the prior year due to limitations in the number of police officers. The most often occurring index crimes were those involving physical harm and theft, whereas the majority of non-index crimes were those involving traffic accidents and other violations of local ordinances. R. Soares (2004) Development has little impact on crime once the existence of the reporting inaccuracy is taken into consideration. Crime rates fall when inequality is decreased, growth is increased, and education levels rise.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The number of crimes that were reported fell in 2020 and 2021. The stringent application of CoViD-19 rules during the pandemic contributes significantly to the decline in crime. Traffic Incident Physical Injuries, acts of lasciviousness in non-index crimes climbed in 2020, and theft in crimes against property increased in 2021, while crimes against persons included rape as the most frequent crime and violations to the special law Anti-VAWC Act of 2004. However, the statistics showed that it's conceivable for crimes to happen again in the years after the outbreak. This study suggests that new preventative measures be implemented in the following years. Other clustering techniques and a comparison of the various outcomes may be used in future research initiatives.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The Commission on Higher Education's Scholarship for Staff and Instructor Knowledge Advancement Program (CHED-SIKAP) gave funding for the author's study on "Analyzing Crime Statistics in the Municipality of San Jose and Goa Camarines Sur, Philippines Ay 2019-2021." The study's final product is this essay. The author also acknowledges Dr. Robino Cawi, a professor at the University of the Cordilleras, for his continued guidance and encouragement in carrying out study. We thank Dr. Raul G.

Bradecina, President of Partido State University, for motivating us to carry out this study.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Braga, A. A. (2005). Hot spots policing and crime prevention: A systematic review of randomized controlled trials. *Journal of Experimental Criminology*, 1(3), 317–342.
- [2]. Broadhurst, R. (2002). Lethal Violence, Crime and State Formation in Cambodia. *Australian & New Zealand Journal of Criminology*, 35(1), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1375/acri.35.1.1>
- [3]. Chalfin, A., & McCrary, J. (2013). *The effect of police on crime: new evidence from US cities, 1960–2010*. National Bureau of Economic Research.
- [4]. Crime in the Philippines - statistics & facts Published by Statista Research Department, Nov 23, 2022 <https://www.statista.com/topics/6994/crime-in-the-philippines/#topicHeaderwrapper>
- [5]. Dio, R. V. ., Apostol, S. M. G. ., & Madrazo, A. L. . (2019). Drug Surrenderers and Crime Statistics During the Implementation of Project Double Barrel (PDB) in the Philippines. *International Journal of Social and Administrative Sciences*, 4(1), 31–43. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.136.2019.41.31.43>
- [6]. Epictetus E. Patalinghug, Crime rates and labor market opportunities in the Philippines: 1970–2008, *Economics Letters*, Volume 113, Issue 2, 2011, Pages 160-164, ISSN 0165-1765, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econlet.2011.07.015>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0165176511002825>)
- [7]. Eric D. Gould, Bruce A. Weinberg, David B. Mustard; Crime Rates and Local Labor Market Opportunities in the United States: 1979–1997. *The Review of Economics and Statistics* 2002; 84 (1): 45–61. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1162/003465302317331919>
- [8]. Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). Special law. In *Merriam-Webster.com legal dictionary*. Retrieved January 16, 2023, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/legal/special%20law>
- [9]. Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). General law. In *Merriam-Webster.com legal dictionary*. Retrieved January 16, 2023, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/legal/general%20law>
- [10]. Rachael Diprose (2007) Physical Safety and Security: A Proposal for Internationally Comparable Indicators of Violence, *Oxford Development Studies*, 35:4, 431-458, DOI: 10.1080/13600810701701913
- [11]. Sherman, L. (1995). Hot Spots of Crime and Criminal Careers of Places. In J. Eck & D. Weisburd (Eds.), *Crime and Place* (pp. 35–52). Police Executive Research Forum.
- [12]. Soares, R. R., (2004) Development, crime and punishment: accounting for the international differences in crime rates, *Journal of Development Economics*, Volume 73, Issue 1, 2004, Pages 155-184, ISSN 0304-3878, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdevec.2002.12.001>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0304387803001330>)

- [13]. Tseloni, A., Mailley, J., Farrell, G., & Tilley, N. (2010). Exploring the international decline in crime rates. *European Journal of Criminology*, 7(5), 375–394. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1477370810367014>
- [14]. Vio Jianu Mojica, Adelbert Choi, Robert Neil Leong & Frumencio Co (2019) Spatial analysis of violent crimes in Metro Manila, Philippines, *International Journal of Comparative and Applied Criminal Justice*, 43:1, 29-47, DOI: 10.1080/01924036.2017.1398669
- [15]. World Bank. <https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/PHL/philippines/crime-rate-statistics>>Philippines Crime Rate & Statistics 1990-2023. www.macrotrends.net. Retrieved 2023-01-16.